

Minimizing Damage in Postbuckling Stiffened Composite Panels: An Optimization Strategy using High Performance Computing

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SUMMARY

A finite-element based optimisation procedure is presented which delays the onset of failure, by skin-stiffener debonding, in a postbuckling stiffened composite panel. A global-local modelling approach, validated using existing experimental results, was linked to a genetic algorithm to optimise the stacking sequence of the panel to increase its damage resistance subject to critical buckling load and prebuckling stiffness constraints. The optimised configuration was one which delayed the onset a secondary instability. This is consistent with earlier studies which showed that mode-jumping was a damage-inducing phenomenon.

Keywords: buckling, postbuckling, stiffened panel, debonding, optimisation

INTRODUCTION

The form of construction of most primary composite aerostructures is still based on a stiffened skin approach. Various experimental programmes [1-5] have demonstrated the ability of these panels to support load beyond initial skin-buckling when loaded in compression. When such a stiffened composite panel buckles, the relatively weak skin-stiffener interface, in a secondary bonded, co-bonded or co-cured panel, is vulnerable to the through-thickness stresses arising from local buckling deformations. The postbuckling behaviour of stiffened composite structures is further complicated by the possibility of sudden changes in buckling mode-shape [1, 2, 6]. The energy dissipated during a mode-jump occurring at a high loading may be enough to initiate unstable crack propagation at the relatively weak skin-stiffener interface causing catastrophic collapse [1, 4, 7].

If the aerospace industry is to achieve its goal of reducing the extent of experimental testing through the development of robust numerical modelling tools, then it is imperative that reliable analytical and numerical tools are developed which can accurately capture the postbuckling behaviour of composite structures. Furthermore, when designing composite structures, the increased number of design variables offered by the use of composites adds greater complexity to the design process, but also adds new possibilities to achieve more efficient designs. Two optimisation algorithms, simulated annealing [8] and genetic algorithms (GAs) [9, 10] are ideally suited to nonlinear optimisation problems [11] and have found extensive use in the field of optimisation of composite structures. In particular, considerable work has been reported

in the literature on the use of GAs to optimise composite laminates to meet a variety of objectives and constraints [12-15].

The aim of the present work was to develop a robust FE based optimisation methodology [16, 17] for composite structures which considered failure by skin-stiffener debonding. This involved three major steps. The first was the accurate modelling of the composite structure to be optimised. This was achieved via FE models of various existing structures and validated against experimental results. The second was the modelling of failure, focusing on delamination at skin-stiffener interfaces. The third step was the optimisation procedure. Use of the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) High Performance Computing (HPC) facility in Canberra, Australia made it possible to overcome the otherwise prohibitive computational costs often associated with coupling optimisation routines with detailed non-linear FE models and exploring large design spaces.

I-STIFFENED PANEL

Experimental procedure

An I-stiffened panel was manufactured by BAE Systems [18] and had a length of 850 mm and width of 604 mm. The stiffeners, whose location is shown in Figure 1, were secondary bonded to the skin using FM-300 adhesive. The loaded edges, at the ends of the panel, were potted in a mixture of epoxy resin and fibreglass, before being machined flat and parallel to ensure uniform loading, reducing the effective span of the panel to 790mm. Skin and stiffener dimensions and lay-up are illustrated in Figure 2(a), while the ply drop-off scheme in the stiffener flanges is as show in Figure 2 (b). Table 1 shows the unidirectional properties of the T300/914C material system used for the panel. Back-to-back strain gauges and LVDTs, whose locations are shown in Figure 1, were mounted on the panel to monitor strains and out-of-plane displacements. Shadow Moiré fringe patterns were observed to capture the qualitative buckling behaviour of the I-stiffened panel as it was compression tested under displacement control with a crosshead displacement of 0.04 mm/min.

Figure 1 Panel effective test section dimensions with strain gauge and LVDT locations.

Figure 2 I-stiffeners: (a) dimension and lay-up with (b) ply drop-off detail.

Table 1: Nominal material data for T300/914 unidirectional prepreg.

Property	Value
Longitudinal tensile modulus	135 GPa
Longitudinal compressive modulus	120 GPa
Transverse tensile modulus	9 GPa
Transverse compressive modulus	9 GPa
In-plane shear modulus	4.9 GPa
Poisson's ratio	0.28
Ply thickness	0.125 mm

Experimental results

Initial buckling of the panel occurred at a loading of approximately 120 kN. The Moiré fringe patterns of Figure 3 (a) shows a fully developed five half-wave buckling configuration. At a buckling load of 120 kN back-to-back strain gauge readings for strain gauge pair 3-4 began to diverge significantly due to the curvature of the skin at the buckle crests, Figure 4. Buckling was also evident from the LVDT A readings shown in Figure 5.

At 241 kN the I-stiffened panel exhibited a sudden mode-jump to a six half-wave configuration in all three skin bays as evidenced in Figure 3 (b). Out-of-plane displacements recorded at LVDT A reduced significantly, Figure 5, and Figure 4 shows a reduction in the recorded strains. Further sudden mode-jumps were observed first in the left bay at 473 kN and then in the right bay at 486 kN. These corresponded to a change into a seven half-wave configuration. Figure 3(c) shows that the middle bay remained in the six half-wave configuration.

Figure 3 Moiré fringe patterns for I-stiffened panel at a loading of (a) 160 kN, (b) 242 kN, (c) 487 kN.

Panel collapse occurred at 525 kN following audible acoustic emission occurring on several occasions between loadings of 518 kN and 524 kN. Ultrasonic scans were conducted on the panel to attempt to assess the mechanisms of crack initiation and propagation that led to failure, in view of experimental work which had indicated that damage starts via the debonding of the skin-stiffener interface at positions of node and anti-node lines [4, 5, 19, 20]. Ultrasonic scans at anti-node lines, where transverse bending moments are at a maximum, indicated possible delamination. This suggested a failure mechanism starting with delamination of the skin-stiffener interface under the

stiffener web, subsequently causing the skin to buckle away from the stiffener, peeling off the rest of the stiffener and eventually leading to collapse [18, 21].

Figure 4 Experimental and numerical results for back-to-back strain gauge pair SG 3-4.

Figure 5 Experimental and numerical out-of-plane displacements at location A.

Finite element models

A global-local submodelling approach in ABAQUS [22] was used to predict the panel's buckling and postbuckling behaviour and capture the delamination at the skin-stiffener interface. The global model contained 2,800 conventional shell elements with reduced integration, each having four nodes and six degrees-of-freedom at each node. One integration point per ply was used through the thickness. Boundary conditions were imposed on the global model to replicate the experimental configuration, and linear buckling analyses were conducted to find the buckling load and mode shapes of the panel. A linear superposition of the first three buckle modes was used to impose out-of-plane geometric imperfections in the panel model with a maximum amplitude of

3% of the skin thickness. This allowed the nonlinear solver to trace the full postbuckling response of the panel.

The local model was a detailed model of a representative section of the panel and was driven directly by the global model solution. The length of the local model was chosen such that it encompassed two node lines and an anti-node line in the five half-wave buckled configuration of the panel. The width was chosen to guarantee that the displacements due to buckle crests and troughs in the global model could be mapped into the local model using the global-local submodelling approach. The local model contained 1,344 eight-node linear brick elements and 84 six-node triangular elements, required for the correct modelling of the ply drop-offs, in the stiffener part, while the skin was modelled using 924 eight-node linear brick elements. Each element had one integration point per ply through the thickness. A total of 336 interface elements were introduced at the skin-stiffener interface of the local model to investigate the debonding that may occur at the skin-stiffener interface and which is known to be a precursor to final collapse. Interface elements combine aspects of both strength-based analysis to predict the onset of stiffness degradation, and fracture mechanics to predict the propagation of delamination. The traction-separation law used for the interface elements was bilinear, representing initial linear elastic behaviour followed by initiation and evolution of damage [23]. The properties assigned to the interface elements were taken from experimental values [24] relating to FM-300 adhesive and are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: FM-300 skin-stiffener interface properties.

Property	Value
σ_{0I}	61 MPa
$\sigma_{0II}/\sigma_{0III}$	49.8 MPa
G_{IC}	532 J/m ²
G_{IIC}/G_{IIIC}	2,358 J/m ²
Film thickness	0.13 mm
ν_{12}	0.28

Global model results

A critical buckling load of 125.2 kN was predicted by the ABAQUS linear buckling analysis, which compared well with the experimentally obtained value of 120 kN. The non-linear solver predicted the panel to buckle into a five half-wave configuration as shown in Figure 6 (a). This can be compared to the Moiré fringe patterns at a loading of 160kN shown in Figure 3 (a). The occurrence of buckling at a loading of 125.2 kN was confirmed by both the numerical strain and out-of-plane displacement results of Figure 4 and Figure 5 respectively. The nonlinear solver predicted the panel to mode-jump at a load of 262 kN, in good agreement with the experimental value of 241 kN. As in the experiment, this consisted of a sudden jump of all three skin bays from the five half-wave configuration to a six half-wave as shown in Figure 6 (b). Strains in the middle of the central bay at positions SG3-4 (Figure 4) were suddenly reduced as buckle crests changed location.

After the mode-jump, the correlation between numerical and experimental values was not as accurate as in the initial postbuckling regime. Figure 6 (c) shows how the FE panel remained in the six half-wave configuration, whilst in the experiment the right and

left skin-bays were seen to jump to a seven half-wave configuration with the middle skin bay showing an elongated top buckle as it interacted with the side bays. Numerical strain and out-of-plane displacements showed no more sudden changes in values as the panel remained in the same configuration with buckle crests growing in size.

There are several reasons why the FE global model was not able to capture the mode-jumps that occurred in the right and left skin-bays prior to the experimental panel collapse. There is inevitable microcracking in the experimental panel that occurs at high loadings as was evidenced by acoustic emission being reported prior to complete failure, and such microcracking may modify the actual stiffness of the panel. One such acoustic emission event corresponded to a loud bang as the panel jumped from the five to the six half-wave configuration. Some local damage may have occurred at this point and influenced how the panel behaved at higher loadings. Furthermore, evidence of skin-stiffener debonding and other delaminations were observed to have occurred in the panel at failure. The global FE model had no capability to model such phenomena which may be influential precursors to the eventual overall collapse of the panel, as may be seen when discussing the numerically predicted results of the local model.

Figure 6 Out-of-plane displacement contours, from FE global model, at a loading of (a) 160 kN, (b) 265 kN, (c) 487 kN. Deformation scale factor 5.

Local model results

Investigation of the damage at the skin-stiffener interface, as the panel was loaded in compression was made possible by the inclusion of interface elements in the local FE model. Figure 7 shows the deformed shape of the local model, together with the degradation in the interface elements for the same load levels as Figure 6. Most stiffener elements are removed for visualization purposes. Since the local model was being driven directly by the global model, the interface element damage was directly influenced by the buckling and postbuckling behaviour of the whole I-stiffened panel. Just after buckling, no damage was observed in the interface elements. Increasing the load meant that the buckle crests increased in magnitude, still remaining in the five half-wave configuration. At a loading of 160 kN, shown in Figure 7 (a), some initial stiffness degradation was seen to occur directly under the stiffener web at a location corresponding to a stiffener anti-node line. This correlated well with experimental observations [4]. As the skin buckled, a bending moment in the stiffener web was generated which increased linearly with a maximum occurring at the base of the stiffener web. This bending moment arose from the constraint applied by the torsional stiffness of the stiffener cap. Experimentally, this resulted in the formation of cracks at the triangular region underneath the web and bounded on each side of the stiffener

flanges, which propagated along the skin stiffener interface. As the loading was increased further, the panel exhibited the mode-jump to the six half-wave configuration. This resulted in the relocation of node and anti-node lines as shown in Figure 7 (b) for 265 kN load. Due to this new buckle configuration, the extent of skin-stiffener debonding also changed. The position of the new anti-node lines resulted in the damage “spreading” along the panel stiffener length direction to this new location. In Figure 7 (c) at a loading of 500 kN, the buckle crests increased in magnitude, still in the six-half wave configuration, and debonding began to spread across the skin-stiffener interface towards the flange edges. At 800 kN, Figure 7 (d), the stiffener was almost completely debonded.

Figure 7 FE local model of skin-stiffener interface element damage at a loading of (a) 160 kN, (b) 265 kN, (c) 500 kN, (d) 800kN.

THE OPTIMISATION PROCEDURE

The objective of the optimisation procedure was to increase the I-stiffened panel’s damage resistance in the postbuckling regime. This was done by simultaneously tailoring the lay-up of the panel skin and flanges to minimize the growth of damage at the skin-stiffener interface. During the optimisation process each different design corresponding to a specific lay-up was evaluated by means of the global and local FE models. Changes in stacking sequence of the panel, determined by the optimisation procedure, were reflected in both the global and local models. Each design evaluation required a solution to the global model to find the panel’s postbuckling response followed by a solution to the local model to investigate skin-stiffener debonding.

The objective function for the problem was chosen to be the sum of the damage variables of the interface elements in the local model. The design variables for the optimisation were the ply orientations of the plies in the panel skin and flanges. Ply orientations were allowed to take values of 0° , 45° , -45° , 90° , commonly used in industry, transforming the optimisation problem into a nonlinear integer programming problem. Modifying the panel lay-up changes both its buckling and postbuckling

characteristics, and hence it was not sufficient to just minimize the extent of element degradation at the skin-stiffener interface. Constraints were introduced on the pre-buckling stiffness and buckling load of the panel to guarantee a feasible design. As was mentioned earlier, the original I-stiffened panel had a buckling load of 125.2 kN and prebuckling stiffness of 140.9 kN/mm. Constraints were set by penalizing those designs which had a buckling load or prebuckling stiffness 10% less than that of the original (baseline) I-stiffened panel.

Having defined the objective function, design variables, and constraints to be used, an optimisation strategy to find the best stacking sequence in the I-stiffened panel was formulated to increase the panel's damage resistance in postbuckling. The optimisation strategy adopted was that of minimizing the sum of the total damage in all of the interface elements at the skin-stiffener interface in the local FE model. The experimentally observed collapse load of 525 kN was used to compare the extent of skin-stiffener interface damage. The optimisation was done using a GA constructed in MATLAB [25] which linked directly to ABAQUS for function evaluations [16, 17]. Linking a GA with FE models for function evaluations is often prohibitive due to the repetitive number of computationally expensive numerical simulations required to converge to an optimum solution. The NCI HPC cluster was utilised to speed up function evaluations for the simultaneous optimisation of both the panel flanges and skin for damage resistance in postbuckling, searching a design space of over 4,200 million individuals. This facility is an SGI Altix 3700 Bx2 cluster with 1928 1.6 GHz Itanium2 processors and 5.6Tbytes of memory. Between 16 and 64 parallel processors were used for this work.

OPTIMISATION RESULTS

Optimal panel lay-up

Execution of the GA to find an optimum skin lay-up led to convergence after ten generations. The complete lay-up for the optimised panel is shown in Table 3. Comparing the lay-ups of the optimized panel in Table 3 and the non-optimized panel in Figure 2 it can be noted how changes in stiffener flange lay-up as a result of the orientation also alter the lay-up of the stiffener webs and caps.

Table 3: Optimised panel lay-up.

	Lay-up
Skin	[0,45,-45,45,-45 ₃ ,90] _s
Flange	[0 ₃ ,90,0,45,-45,45]
Web	[0 ₄ ,90,0,45 ₂ ,-45 ₂ ,45]
Cap	[0 ₄ ,90,0,45 ₂ ,-45 ₂ ,45,90,0 ₃ ,90 ₂ ,0 ₄ ,90 ₂ ,0 ₂]

Table 4 compares the performance of the optimum panel to the original non-optimised configuration. The linear buckling analysis predicted a buckling load of 126.7 kN compared to 125.2 kN for the non-optimised configuration. This meant that the optimised panel actually had a buckling load 1.2% higher than that of the original panel. The prebuckling stiffness was reduced by 9.6% from 190.3 kN/mm to 172.0 kN/mm whilst the postbuckling stiffness by 8.5%, from 157.1 kN/mm to 143.8 kN/mm. The

total damage at the skin-stiffener interface, corresponding to the objective function, was reduced by 43.3%, showing the effectiveness of the GA in finding a new skin configuration to increase the damage resistance of the panel in its postbuckling regime.

Table 4: Comparison of optimised and non-optimised panels.

	Optimised	Non-optimised	% Diff.
Buckling load (kN)	126.7	125.2	+1.2%
Prebuckling stiffness (kN/mm)	172.0	190.3	-9.6%
Postbuckling stiffness (kN/mm)	143.8	157.1	-8.5%
Interface element damage	53.1	93.8	-43.3%

Optimized panel postbuckling behaviour

Figure 8 shows the response of the optimized panel compared to the non-optimised panel. These results showed that the optimised configuration of the panel still buckled in the five half-wave configuration as seen in Figure 8 (a). Note also that the locations of the buckle crests and troughs, on the optimised panel, have been inverted. As the loading was increased, the non-optimised panel mode-jumped to the six half-wave configuration at 262 kN. This is in contrast to the optimised panel which maintained its five half-wave configuration.

Figure 8 Comparison of deformed shape (scale factor five) and out-of-plane displacement (mm) contour plots for non-optimised and optimised panel at loading: (a) 160 kN, (b) 265 kN, (c) 487 kN.

Optimised panel skin-stiffener interface damage

The local model results for the optimised skin lay-up panel were also compared to those of the non-optimised I-stiffened panel to assess the extent of skin-stiffener debonding. Figure 9 shows the skin-stiffener debonding at various different load levels. Damage was localized at the location of buckle anti-node lines where bending moments are at a maximum directly under the stiffener web. When the non-optimised panel mode-jumped in Figure 9 (b), the damage spread in the longitudinal direction due to the appearance of new node and anti-node lines. This did not happen in the optimised skin lay-up panel as the buckle crest grew deeper but remained in the same location as visible in Figure 9 (c). Damage spread outwards from the web towards the stiffener flanges but remained localized. Hence it was the different postbuckling behaviour of the optimised panel, exhibiting a delayed mode-jump, that was responsible for increasing the damage resistance.

The growth of the debond at the skin stiffener-interface, as predicted by the local FE model, was compared with the non-optimised and optimised designs. Figure 10 shows a plot of the total interface damage against the applied load for both the non-optimised panel and the panel with the optimised skin lay-up. It is clear the two panels show very similar damage levels until a load of 262 kN when the non-optimised panel mode-jumps from the five half-wave to the six half-wave configuration. As was seen in Figure 9, this led to the damage spreading lengthwise across the interface due to the appearance of new buckle crests. At the original panel collapse load of 525 kN for which the optimisation was conducted, the total interface damage for the optimised configuration was reduced by 43.3%.

Figure 9 Comparison of interface element damage for non-optimised and optimised finite element models: (a) 160 kN, (b) 265 kN, (c) 500 kN.

Figure 10 Comparison of skin-stiffener debond growth in non-optimised and optimised panels.

Comparison with previous optimisations

The use of an HPC cluster meant that it was possible to conduct the optimisation presented in the search for the optimal panel layup in a design space of over 4,200 million individuals. This allowed for the simultaneous optimisation of the panel skin and flange lay-ups rather than being limited to optimisation of a certain section of the panel so as to limit the size of the design space as was done in previous optimisations [16, 17]. Table 5 below compares the results of the simultaneous optimisation of the panel skin and flanges to that of individual optimisations on the panel skin layup and flange lay-up.

Table 5: Comparison of optimisation methods.

Optimization type	Optimisation design space	Interface element damage	% Diff.
No optimisation	-	93.8	-
Flange layup only [16]	65,536	81.9	-12.7
Skin layup only [17]	65,536	55.0	-41.4
Skin and flange layup	4.296×10^6	53.1	-43.3

Table 5 shows that allowing the optimisation to search for a revised skin and flange lay-up simultaneously results in an optimized panel configuration with the greatest reduction in skin-stiffener interface damage. A skin-only optimisation has a greater impact on damage reduction than a flange layup only optimisation, indicating that changes in skin lay-up have the greatest effect on the postbuckling response of the panel. Both the skin-only optimisation and the simultaneous flange and skin layup optimisation delayed the secondary instability in the panel (mode-jump from five to six half-wave configuration) resulting in the growth of damage at the skin-stiffener interface being reduced. The individual optimisation of the flange layup however did not result in as great reductions in skin-stiffener interface damage. The optimised flange lay-up panel buckled straight into a six half-wave configuration, but the optimisation still lead to a configuration where a secondary instability does not occur, at least prior to the experimental collapse load of the panel.

Conclusions

An automated optimisation procedure was presented to optimise the lay-up of an I-stiffened composite panel to increase its damage resistance in the postbuckling regime. The objective of the optimisation was defined as the minimization of the total damage at the skin-stiffener interface, whilst the design variables were taken as the orientation of the plies in both the stiffener flanges and panel skin. Constraints on buckling load and prebuckling stiffness were also imposed to guarantee a feasible optimal design. At the experimentally observed collapse load of 525 kN for which the optimisation was conducted, the optimised panel showed a level of skin-stiffener debonding 43.3% lower than that observed in the original panel. The increased damage resistance of the optimised panel was attributed to the fact that the mode-jump from five to six half-waves observed in the original panel was delayed to a level beyond the experimental collapse load of the panel. Such a mode-jump creates new buckle node and anti-node lines, which are critical locations for damage initiation, resulting in a sudden increase in

skin-stiffener interface damage. Optimisation results were compared to two other optimisations conducted by the authors on the same panel but which were limited by the computational power available and hence design space of the optimisation.

The major advantage of the optimisation procedure presented is its flexibility. Different constraints could be added to the optimisation to deal with specific design needs, and the same concept of coupling a GA and FE analyses in an autonomous fashion could be used to optimise a different structure for a specific objective and various design variables.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by an award under the Merit Allocation Scheme on the NCI National Facility at the ANU.

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